

Students Mark Prediction using Machine Learning

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Abstract: For students in school, predicting academic success is a *crucial* duty. Time spent studying and average grade are elements that affect a student's academic achievement.

The class instructor should be informed in advance about the students'

academic performance in order to improve performance and reduce dropout rates. In this study, a decision tree approach and a linear regression model are used to predict students' academic achievement using machine learning. Based on accuracy score, the performance of an algorithm has been assessed. In this dataset, we have 26 students with some information on student's study time and average mark. From these statistics, we seek to understand what factors influence student performance and help them get high marks.

Keywords: Data mining; School students; study time; Linear regression; Decision tree.

I. INTRODUCTION

Although there are many uses for the internet, students rank academic usage as its top priority. It might be difficult for students to understand the wide variety of classes that make up their core curriculum while they attend school. They chose the internet as a result since it is a storehouse of knowledge about the topic of their inquiry. People are compelled to rely entirely on the internet in today's society since it plays such a large role in their daily life. Since kids use the internet for a number of things, including communicating, getting notes for their studies, doing projects, and other pertinent activities, students are mostly to blame for this. Nearly all students are required to take the relevant subject, which is. It is nearly always necessary to take the course that is closely relevant to the field that each student has chosen.

The courses cover all of the foundational and essential material from each field. As a result, there is a chance that students will use the internet for reasons other than their studies, such as recreation. Academic performance prediction of students has long been noted and is considered as an important study subject in various domains since it assists both educators and students. Teachers can use the projected outcomes to estimate how many students will perform well, averagely, or poorly in a particular class in order to take the proper action. A student's academic achievement may be predicted using a variety of categories. Data analysis may be used to discover helpful information and trends that can be used in the future predictive analysis. A prediction model may be developed using a variety of techniques, including classification, regression, categorization, and the development of prediction rules [3]. Predictions are

frequently made using the classification. Decision trees, neural networks [5, SVM [8, Naive Bayes], and KNN [9] are a few of the methods. Our major goal is to provide a model that can be used with decision trees and regression analysis to forecast children's academic improvement. The academic development of the children has been predicted using a variety of mathematical techniques, such as logistic regression, linear regression, and regression analysis.

II. RELATED WORKS

To forecast certain critical information, many techniques or approaches were used. Health forecasting is one usage. It is possible to predict many illnesses in the medical area before looking into it. As a result, they utilized a data mining approach called association rule mining, which maps the medical data to the transaction and produces association rules. Some researchers focused on heart disease and the building of rules in medical data to forecast the incidence of disease [2]. The relationship between the item sets may be ascertained through association rule mining.

The most effective data mining approach provided the highest percentage of accurate predictions for heart disease, according to calculations done by the authors using a variety of data mining techniques, including samples for further understanding.

Application of data mining techniques to forecast students' academic progress is the main objective of the present study. Here are several academics that have discussed how data mining techniques may improve academic performance in children. In order to forecast pupils' academic progress, Oloruntoba et al. published research in 2017. The study found a relationship between students' academic success and test results. A support vector machine approach was used to build the model, and it was contrasted with various classification techniques. The end result has demonstrated that SVM classification accuracy is significantly higher than that of the other methodologies.

The use of data mining techniques for university management was the major subject of a research paper carried out by Dorina Kabakchieva of the Bulgarian University in 2012. The categorization results generated by the selected data mining techniques don't demonstrate any significant findings. Zlatko (2010) examined the demographics of the students and the learning

environment that corresponded with them in order to analyze how these factors affect students' success rates in their academic endeavours. The findings demonstrate that the CART algorithm—which yields a total percentage of 60.5%—is utilised to predict the student category and to differentiate between successful and failed students. It is not sufficiently thorough to allow for differentiation between successful and unsuccessful students.

III. OBJECTIVE OF THE PRESENT STUDY

The primary goal of the current project is to create a collection of decision trees and linear regression models to predict students' academic success.

- x_1 : To predict the mark
- x_2 : To predict the mark based on their study time
- x_3 : Compare with average mark of the students
- x_4 : To predict the score of the students
- y : Result

where x is the model's result and the variable from to indicates the student's study time. The goal of the study is predicting the mark based on study time and average mark. Some of the research problems covered in the current study include formulating the equations for predictive models and evaluating the predictive models' accuracy.

IV. OVERVIEW OF ALGORITHM

Regression is a statistical method for figuring out how the variables in the data relate to one another. The relationship between the dependent variable and independent variables, sometimes referred to as predictors, is its main focus. It is useful to comprehend how the value of the dependent variable changes when the independent variable is changed. An equation containing the independent variables, certain coefficients, and the slope value is built using the value of the independent variable. There are many different regression methods available. One such method is the mostly predictive linear regression methodology. One dependent variable and one or more independent variables are investigated using the linear regression method. Equation (1) gives a simple linear regression with one dependent variable and one independent variable:

$$y = c + m * x \tag{1}$$

when c is a constant, m is the regression coefficient, x is the value of the independent variable, and y is the predicted value of the dependent variable. Several linear regression approaches include simple linear regression, multiple linear regression, logistic regression, ordinal regression, multinomial regression, and discriminant analysis. In our research, we use multiple linear regression. Multiple linear regression is used for datasets with a single dependent variable and more than two

independent variables. The equation for multiple linear regression is given by equation (2):

$$y' = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + b_4x_4 + \dots + b_kx_k \tag{2}$$

The following steps can be used to calculate the multiple linear regression:

$$X = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & x_{11} & x_{21} & \dots & x_{k1} \\ 1 & x_{12} & x_{22} & \dots & x_{k2} \\ 1 & x_{13} & x_{23} & \dots & x_{k3} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ 1 & x_{1n} & x_{2n} & \dots & x_{kn} \end{bmatrix}$$

$$B = (X^T X)^{-1} X^T \cdot Y \tag{3}$$

$$B = \begin{bmatrix} b_1 \\ b_2 \\ b_3 \\ \vdots \\ b_k \end{bmatrix}$$

$$X^T = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 1 & \dots & 1 \\ x_{11} & x_{12} & x_{13} & \dots & x_{1n} \\ x_{21} & x_{22} & x_{23} & \dots & x_{2n} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ x_{k1} & x_{k2} & x_{k3} & \dots & x_{kn} \end{bmatrix} \quad Y = \begin{bmatrix} y_1 \\ y_2 \\ y_3 \\ \vdots \\ y_k \end{bmatrix}$$

includes the transposed matrix of the matrix X , where X contains the values of the independent variables and Y contains the values of the dependent variables. The predicted coefficients of the independent variables are presented in a matrix form in equation (4). Consequently, these variables are expressed as follows:

$$y' = a + b_1x_1 + b_2x_2 + b_3x_3 + \dots + b_kx_k \tag{5}$$

We may develop the equation for a regression line with the aid of the training dataset, and we can forecast the correctness of the predicted equation using the test dataset. To obtain the projected scores, the test dataset is used as input for the aforementioned Equation (5).

V. Decision Tree

Decision trees were mostly used to solve classification and regression issues. It is a supervised learning technique. It's sometimes referred to as dealing with classification problems. It has a tree-structured classifier. It has leaf nodes, branches, and interior nodes. In contrast to internal nodes, which describe the dataset's properties, branching, and decision-making processes, leaf nodes each indicate the conclusion. The two nodes that make up a decision tree are the decision node and the leaf node. Decision nodes are used to make all decisions and have many branches, whereas leaf nodes just show the choice's outcome and have no branching.

To define information gain precisely, we need to define a measure commonly used in information theory

called entropy that measures the level of impurity in a group of examples. Mathematically, it is defined as:

$$\text{Entropy: } \sum I = 1 - p * \log_2(p)$$

pi=Probabilityofclassi

Since, the basic version of the ID3 algorithm deal with the case where classification is either positive or negative, we can define entropy as:

$$\text{Entropy}(S) = -p_+ \log_2 p_+ - p_- \log_2 p_-$$

p_+ is the proportion of positive examples in S

p_- is the proportion of negative examples in S

VI. DATA COLLECTION

Sn no	Hour	Mark
1	2.5	9
2	5.1	25

A detail was created based on the study to gather information regarding the pupils' academic achievement. A total of 26 students were chosen at random from the group, making it a likely method of gathering information from the students for data collecting. Mark deals with information on the pupils, including information on their study habits and average grade. An analytical prediction model is created using the data. The data about the students are displayed in the table.

VII. RESEARCH METHOD OF THE PRESENT STUDY

For the purposes of developing and validating the projected model, a total of 26 students were taken into account over the appropriate study period. The research methodology's flow is described in the steps that follow.

- Gathering information from the students based on their academic success up to the present study time and the typical test mark. Analysing the data that has been obtained and understanding it
- Choose the gathered data and divide it into a training and testing dataset.
- After segmenting the dataset, the training dataset is submitted to a linear regression technique, and predictions are made by examining the test dataset using the decision tree produced from the regression equation and decision tree.

According to the study, the training dataset will contain two different types of students. The categories from the training dataset will be used to forecast the models. The

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flow of the current study's prediction model is shown in Figure 1.

From the whole dataset, a sample category of students is considered for explanation.

Sn no	Study Hours	average mark
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VIII. MODEL VALIDATION

To see how well the model predicts and whether the test data is legitimate, more model validation should be performed.

The primary phase in the mark prediction detection process is model construction. The algorithms are used by the user when developing the model.

1. Import the package that are necessary.

```
#importing needed libraries
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
from sklearn.preprocessing import PolynomialFeatures
```

2. Add the data into a data frame, then get shape of data.

```
[ ] df = pd.read_csv('/content/student.csv')
print("Data imported successfully")

df.head(10)
print(df)
```

```
Data imported successfully
   Hours  Scores
0     2.5     9
1     5.1    25
```

3. The split the dataset into training and testing dataset.

```
] X_train, X_test, Y_train, Y_test = train_test_split(x, y,
                                                    test_size=0.1, random_state=0)
```

```
] lr = LinearRegression().fit(X_train, Y_train)
tree = DecisionTreeRegressor().fit(X_train, Y_train)
```

4. predicted output.

```
[ ] lr_pred = lr.predict(X_test)
tree_pred = tree.predict(X_test)
df = pd.DataFrame({'Actual': Y_test, 'Linear Regression': lr_pred, 'Decision_Tree' : tree_pre
df
```

Actual Linear Regression Decision_Tree

0	5	2.159658	5.0
1	10	22.964257	30.0
2	69	74.363852	85.0

Actual Linear Regression Decision_Tree

0	5	2.159658	5.0
1	10	22.964257	30.0
2	69	74.363852	85.0

5. Graphical representation

6. Accuracy of train dataset using linear regression

```
print(lr.score(x_train,y_train))
```

0.904642202270908

7. Accuracy of train dataset using decision tree

```
print(tree.score(x_train,y_train))
```

0.9975620822243177

Finally calculating the mean absolute error in both algorithms, we can get linear regression is lesser mean absolute error than compared to decision tree.

IX. RESULT

The result shows that mark prediction can be classified as studying hours and average mark based on the dataset given. The dataset contains details about student's study time and their average mark. This model is classified and the mark was correctly detected by the model.

X. CONCLUSION

Numerous data mining techniques may be used to evaluate student performance. Both the decision tree approach and linear regression are used. It included information on how students' academic performance is identified by their study time and average mark. Decision tree and linear regression are the two main techniques. Education might analyse a class's performance in order to enhance the method of instruction. Here we calculating the mean absolute error in both algorithms. Linear regression is less mean absolute error than decision tree. So, the less error is considered as the best accuracy in this model so linear regression is the best model.

XI. REFERENCES

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